

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Using the Tissue Origin Predictor

A web application for predicting the spatial origins of tissue samples

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Introduction

Determining the spatial location from which a human tissue sample was extracted is important for analyses when tissue context matters. Traditional methods rely on textual annotations (e.g., organ or anatomical terms) and lack details on the size, location, and orientation of a tissue sample. The Human Reference Atlas API uses biomarker expression profile similarities to predict three-dimensional tissue locations, a critical improvement for atlas construction and essential for downstream applications like disease diagnostics and targeted treatments.

The Tissue Origin Predictor is a no-code user interface that allows users to upload a cell type population and get a predicted spatial origin 3D volume (Börner et al. 2025). Predictions made with the Tissue Origin Predictor are at the anatomical structure level, not the organ level (Bueckle et al. 2025). In other words, predicted origins are identified to a more granular level than the organ, which is especially important given the diverse anatomy and varying cell type populations found within single organs.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **HRA Technical Lead** oversees the implementation and maintenance of the API and ensures it utilizes the most recent HRApop release.

The **HRApop Lead** guides experimental data acquisition, HRApop computation, and documentation.

The **User** is typically a computational biologist, who utilizes the Tissue Origin Predictor in their browser to identify the location where a dataset was extracted from, if the location has been lost or is unknown.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Technical Lead	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu

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HRApop Lead	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
User	various	various

Relevant Resources

Table 2. Resources used in these procedures.

Name	Purpose	Location
Tissue Origin Predictor	Main deployment.	apps.humanatlas.io/us2/
Documentation	Description and documentation of the Tissue Origin Predictor on the HRA Portal.	humanatlas.io/user-story/2
Tissue Origin Predictor GitHub Repository	Enables prediction of cell location based on biomarker expression profiles.	github.com/x-atlas-consortia/hra-apps/tree/main/applications/us2-cell-to-spatial
HRA API endpoint used by the Tissue Original Predictor	Use the HRA API to return predicted spatial location of a sample based on user's cell type population.	apps.humanatlas.io/api/#post-/hra-pop/cell-summary-report
HRA API endpoint	Use the HRA API to return a list of organs supported in the latest version of HRApop.	apps.humanatlas.io/api/#get-/hra-pop/supported-organs

Procedures

Predicting the origin of a tissue block

The application at apps.humanatlas.io/us2 uses Anatomical Structure Cell Type Populations (ASpop) and Dataset and Extraction Site Cell Type Populations (DESpop) to predict the most similar anatomical structures for which HRApop data exist, the most similar extraction sites, and the most similar HRApop datasets for a user-provided cell type population of a dataset with unknown spatial origin. A screenshot is shown in **Fig. 1**.

- Upload a cell type population. The user can either
 - upload a CSV file with a cell type population for a dataset or
 - use a sample [CSV file](#) with a cell type population for the heart.
- Choose the organ of origin from a dropdown list
- Choose the cell type annotation tool used to create the cell type population (e.g. Azimuth, CellTypist, or popV).
- When clicking the Generate Predictions button, three types of possible spatial origin are presented, all sorted by weighted cosine similarity between the anatomical structure and

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- Document errors by submitting a [GitHub issue](#), or communicate errors to the HRApop Lead or the HRA Technical Lead directly.

References and Resources

Börner, Katy, Philip D. Blood, Jonathan C. Silverstein, et al. 2025. “Human BioMolecular Atlas Program (HuBMAP): 3D Human Reference Atlas Construction and Usage.” *Nature Methods*, March 13, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-024-02563-5>.

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Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center. 2025a.
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<https://github.com/x-atlas-consortia/hra-apps/blob/main/applications/us2-cell-to-spatial/heart-cell-summary.csv>.

Docker: Accelerated Container Application Development. 2025. April 9.
<https://www.docker.com/>.

Glossary

anatomical structure (AS): An anatomical structure is a distinct biological entity with a 3D volume and shape, for example, an organ, functional tissue unit, or cell.

Anatomical Structure Cell Type Populations (ASpop): A collection of cell type annotations for a specific anatomical structure, which captures the number of cells per cell type. Metadata includes an ontology ID, donor sex, anatomical structure label, the cell type annotation tool used to assign cell types, and a list of datasets from which the data was sourced.

application programming interface (API): Software that allows two applications to communicate with each other.

cell type annotation (CTann): The process of identifying and labeling distinct cells. Azimuth and other tools are used to assign cell types to cells from sc/snRNA-seq studies. In the Human Reference Atlas, manually compiled crosswalks are used to assign ontology IDs to these cell types..

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cell type annotation crosswalks: A collection of CSV files that link cell type labels generated using cell type annotation tools to Cell Ontology or Provisional Cell Ontology IDs. This harmonizes cell types across ASCT+B tables and other digital objects that are part of the Human Reference Atlas.

comma-separated values (CSV): This is a text file that has a specific format which allows data to be saved in a table structure.

Dataset and Extraction Site Cell Type Populations (DESpop), formerly “Atlas-Enriched Dataset Graph,” this is a collection of datasets that meet quality criteria and are used for HRApop construction. A snippet of the *DESpop* can be viewed at cns-iu.github.io/hra-cell-type-populations-supporting-information/#for-a-dataset.

Human Reference Atlas Cell Type Populations (HRApop): HRApop is a standardized 3D dataset linking high-quality experimental data to Human Reference Atlas digital objects. HRApop quantifies the number of cells per cell type within anatomical structures, extraction sites, and datasets while harmonizing cell type annotations using crosswalks to common ontologies. HRApop is published as versioned releases and serves as a healthy reference for researchers aiming to clarify mechanisms underlying cellular interactions as well as cellular and tissue level disease progression.

Acknowledgments

The Human Reference Atlas (HRA) is under active development by the Indiana University Mapping Component with expert input from the HRA Editorial Board and in close collaboration with experts from more than 20 consortia. This research has been supported by the NIH Common Fund through the Office of Strategic Coordination/Office of the NIH Director under awards OT2OD033756, OT2OD026671, OT2OD030545, and R03OD039970, by the Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet) Consortium through the Consortium Organization and Data Coordinating Center (CODCC) under award number U24CA268108 and via award U54AG076043, and by the NIDDK under awards U24DK135157 and U01DK133090. The work has also been supported by Kidney Precision Medicine Project grants U2CDK114886 and U01DK133090, and the NIH National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), Department of Health and Human Services under BCBB Support Services Contract HHSN316201300006W/ HHSN27200002, as well as the American Dental Association Science and Research Institute, the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research’s MacMillan Multiscale Human program, and a Stiftung Charité Visiting Fellowship. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health.